

Status of investment and trade in post-conflict Northern Uganda

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Abstract

This paper presents the status of investment and trade in post-conflict Northern Uganda. Administrative trade (formal and informal) and investment (foreign and domestic) from 2005 to-date within and through the region are used to understand the dynamics within a post-conflict lens. While policies and specific regional programs by government exist to rebuild Northern Uganda, they are not specifically supportive of investment and trade taking place in the region; the policies/regulation treat Uganda as homogenous and the programmes have focused on rebuilding local livelihoods and food security through agriculture. Descriptive analysis, first, on the trends and nature of investments reveal that minimal large scale industrial activities are taking place, many are *ad hoc*, largely driven by small-scale/micro investors – (shops, kiosks). Second, trade (formal and informal) is high with South Sudan compared to Democratic Republic of Congo. However, trade through the region is driven by the security conditions in South Sudan. Informal trade was more in foodstuffs and foot wear commodities but these originate from other parts of the country especially, Kampala. In conclusion, we do not observe a clear linkage between investments and trade taking place in the region to local people's welfare. However, few financial institutions are being set up to support traders in cash transactions. Given that policies and programme measures that address access to finance, security of access to land for investment, and infrastructural factors are not necessarily conflict sensitive, these continue to impede growth in investments and trade in Northern Uganda.

Key words: Investment, trade, post-conflict, Northern Uganda

1.0 Introduction

A “Post-conflict” situation is not as easy to define as it sounds. It includes so many peace related milestones: cessation of hostilities and violence; signing of political/peace agreements; demobilisation, disarmament and reintegration; refugee repatriation; establishing a functioning state; achieving reconciliation and societal integration; and economic recovery (Brown *et al.* 2008). As such the end of conflict often presents numerous economic opportunities for the affected region and the surrounding neighbourhood. The daunting task for government is to ensure that persons recovering from conflict are not marginalised during the recovery process. Governments then put in place plans that enhance high investments and build a conflict-resilient community and help persons therein rebuild their livelihoods. Literature postulates that the end of conflict spurs rises in total factor productivity as political and institutional uncertainty linked to war is resolved, hence providing additional incentives for investment and boosting cross border trade (David *et al.* 2011; Collier 2009). Specifically, David *et al.* (2011) show that changes in terms of trade have emerged as the most influential determinant of favourable economic growth in the aftermath of civil war. While Collier (2009) notes that post-conflict situations tend to be linked to commodity export booms, David *et al.* (2011) findings, on the other hand illustrate that pursuing policies that promote export diversification and leverage international markets over the longer term are essential in post-crisis recovery settings. Brown *et al.* (2008) argues that all these variations are relevant to the appropriate design of post-conflict policies/programmes - i.e., policies intended to bring about reconstruction, promote sustainable recovery and to reduce the likelihood of conflict recurrence.

Uganda has tackled the post-conflict recovery question of the northern region¹ since ceasefire in 2006 in Acholi, and Karamoja sub regions. Acholi and Lango sub regions were severely affected from the war caused by the Lord’s Resistance Army (LRA), while Karamoja sub region conflict was related to cattle rustling. Region specific development programmes have been initiated in these areas. The National Development Plans, NDP I and II, recognize the north and, because of the peculiarities therein, the government developed the Peace, Recovery and Development Plan (PRDP). Programme initiatives include the PRDP I, II and now III; Northern Uganda Social Action Fund I and II, *Karamoja Integrated Disarmament and Development Programme* (KIDDP) and the recently concluded Northern Uganda

¹The Northern region is divided into four sub regions: West Nile, Lango, Acholi and Karamoja sub regions. The West Nile Region was *sporadically* affected by the LRA war while the Acholi and Lango sub regions were *severely affected* by the war. The Karamoja sub region had a different type of conflict related to cattle thefts within and across the Kenyan Border in the Turkana region.

Agricultural Livelihoods Recovery Programme (ALREP) and Karamoja Livelihood Programme (KALIP). The latter programmes aimed at contributing to the objectives of the PRDP by focusing on increasing agricultural production and productivity; rebuilding of infrastructure in support of farming and rural communities; enhancing access to finance for agricultural producers, traders and processors; and developing the capacity of local government for effective planning, service delivery, supervision and monitoring. However, specific programme designs do not directly address creating an enabling investment and trade climate with regionally specific policies and regulatory frameworks to support these initiatives. The investment and trade policies² are for national interests and do not spell out how to handle the special case of a post-conflict setting.

Vision 2040 highlights industrialization as one of the opportunities for faster social-economic national development. This will be achieved through: attracting industries which are being transferred from other countries; supporting industries that use our raw materials; training more people to work in industries (easily); constructing good roads, water and electricity to support industries undertake business easily; making Uganda known as a good place to put up industries and do business; and supporting small- and medium-scale industries (Republic of Uganda, 2015). This is a national vision. However, actors need to take note that Uganda's northern region is a small market compared to other parts of the country. While the region has successfully embarked on contributing to the regional East African Community (EAC) integration agenda and has strong commercial links with South Sudan and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), extra-regional trade and investment in viable long-lasting income generating activities remains a challenge within the communities.

According to the 2014 National Population and Housing Census report, the northern region contains around 7,188,139 inhabitants (20.75 percent of Uganda's total population) where 6,275,043 are living in rural areas (representing 87.3 percent of the population in the region). In addition, the working population (14-64 years) in the region is highly uneducated especially among the youth as they missed out on acquiring a skill in their formative years. The population with no formal education is highest in the districts of Northern Uganda that were severely affected by war (UNDP 2015). Such population characteristics have serious implications for industrialization, which is driven by success in investment and trade, given the nature of human capital available to work in established industries. Since the withdrawal of the LRA rebels from Northern Uganda, there has been an increase in trade going

² National Trade policy; Uganda Industrial Policy; Competitive Investment Climate Strategies (CICS I & II); Buy Uganda Build Uganda, 2015 Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Policy 2015; Medium Term Competitiveness Strategy (MTCS); Investment Code Act 1991.

through the region with informal exports from Uganda to Sudan increasing from an estimated US\$7.8 million in 2006, to US\$8.6 million in 2007 (Carrington 2009). Furthermore, during the early recovery period, trade was central to job creation and increased government revenue, whilst also “giving small-scale traders and farmer’s much-needed cash”.

In this context, analysing the nature of investment and trade will enable stakeholders to better understand the sector specific trends performance and constraints, and will also suggest policy options aimed at ensuring that these activities if enhanced can foster strategic industrialization in the region. Thus, the paper presents Northern region-specific investment and trade outcomes. This exercise is fully descriptive but enables us to explore the overall competitiveness of Northern Uganda since conflict. Investment and trade performance are analysed along two dimensions that, together, give a fairly comprehensive picture of competitiveness of the region: (i) the composition (volume and value); and (ii) the degree of diversification across products and markets in some insistence.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 puts into context the status of Northern Uganda to-date and section 3 discusses the approach and data and its sources used in the analysis. Section 4 is the anchor of the paper as it provides findings and discusses results in two subsections 4.1 and 4.2 on the key issues of investment and trade performance within and through the region. Conclusions are provided in section 5.

2.0 Status of Northern Uganda to date

Northern Uganda is the second poorest region of Uganda – 43 percent of its people are poor – and poverty has actually increased in recent years, in contrast to the country overall (which is 19 percent poor [UBOS 2014]). According to a GoU/DFID (2014) report, the region’s Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita is equivalent to that of the very poorest countries in the world, such as Somalia, and poverty rates are more than twice Uganda’s average. In order to catch up with the rest of Uganda by 2040, the region would need to grow as fast as China has managed since 1980. Northern Uganda is dependent on rain-fed, low-productivity smallholder agriculture, which keeps people poor, and highly vulnerable to climate variability and change. Northern Uganda is currently capitalising on its ‘*post-conflict bounce*’, and is expected to maintain GDP growth at around 6 percent in coming years (GoU/DFID 2014). In particular, the procurement and processing of agricultural produce within the region and grain trading appear to be strong growth areas. Agri-processing has been identified³ as one of Uganda’s and the

³ For example, in Hausmann *et al.* (2014), ‘How should Uganda Grow’; Harvard University

regions' major proximate stepping stones on the path to industrialization and growth.

Evidence from Northern Uganda suggests an agri-business-led response, as opposed to a response focusing directly on farmers and farmer groups, as an effective way to reduce yield gaps and increase value-adding processing. While on a positive track, growth in the North is subject to major risks such as conflict in neighbouring regions and poor management of the economy by national and local governments. For example, the most recent conflict in South Sudan in July 2016 led to almost all Ugandan traders and business men to be evacuated from the country under army escort. Trade, both informal and formal was paralysed and still is. The massive, complex and numerous market failures in the northern agro-economy, linked to land, finance, energy, infrastructure and regulatory and standards failures, make growth-acceleration very challenging especially in fostering investment and trade in the region. It stands, however, in a crucial space linking South Sudan and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) to the Ugandan economy.

The North has the lowest value-added per acre of cultivated land in Uganda, less than a third of the national average. The Northern Ugandan economy is very weak in its structure, despite recent growth. The region only represents 4.5 percent of Uganda's exports (GoU/DFID, 2014), despite its proximity to major export markets in the region. Infrastructure, government services and skills are all weaker in the North.

The current status of the Northern economy is summarised in Figure 1. The North accounts for 24 percent of Uganda's population, and only 9 percent of its GDP (GoU/DFID 2014). In addition, Gross Value Addition (GVA) contribution to services and industry is low at 7 percent and 6 percent, respectively, with corresponding employment in both sectors at 9 percent and 10 percent, respectively. Meanwhile, the region's contribution to GVA and employment in agriculture, forestry and fishing is at 17 percent and 30 percent, respectively. Such facts point to agriculture being the key sector in unlocking the region's development potential. Using the Census of Business Enterprises (COBE) survey, only 3 percent of businesses are in the north and the Business Inquiry indicates that only 6 percent are formal versus the 14 percent that are informal (ibid). The GoU/DFID (2014) report characterizes typical businesses in the North as follows:

Most businesses are small, informal, insular, lack growth ambitions, do not export and are dependent on internal funds... most sales are just within the same district the business is operating, which means growth is limited by local demand... Creating more businesses, growing existing businesses, attracting larger firms and reversing the insular nature of businesses are a key challenge (GoU/DFID 2014, xxiv).

The still on-going uncertainty in the neighboring South Sudan since July 2016 does not board well for the region’s investment and trade potential which is still already fragile.

Figure 1: Northern Uganda’s share out of selected national indicators

Source: UBOS, UNRA, Oxford Economics

In a nutshell, given that Northern Uganda suffered extensively from the civil conflict between the Lord’s Resistance Army (LRA) and Ugandan National forces between 1987 and 2006, this implies that a wide area of the region was affected by displacement and disruption, and a generation has grown up without the commercial and agricultural skills of their forbearers (Bozzoli et al. 2011). War largely affected their formative years, thus majority of the youth today in the north missed out on education, and with their low levels of literacy, stigma and skills, they normally find it difficult to get employed especially in the formal sector (UNDP 2015). Often, the youth from the region have been referred to as a “lost generation”. Catching up with the rest of Uganda would require widespread and dramatic economic transformation, matching the fastest transitions of global economic history.

The Government has committed to achieving such a transformation and has been providing targeted economic recovery support to the region since the end of the conflict in 2006 through various programmes such as PRDP, NUSAF, ALREP and KALIP, all largely focusing on revamping agricultural activities and infrastructural development and to a small extent transparency governance aspects and fostering investments and trade. Northern Uganda has been enjoying strong economic growth since the end of the conflict, but this is from a very low base (GoU/DFID

2014), and can be characterised as a post-conflict bounce (Collier 2009), which is unlikely to be sustained without radical from “business as usual” to “business un-usual” from a policy and programme inclusive widespread and rapid investment and business growth.

A review of national policies and programmes (highlighted and not comprehensively reviewed herein) that address investment and trade do not specifically show the pathways of how these sectors will be specifically handled in post conflict Northern Uganda. While arguments can be made that it is not prudent to have policies and regulations that address the Northern Uganda question alone, it is, however, not sufficient in treating regions or groups of people as homogeneous. It is through specialised regional programmes that such peculiarities can be addressed (Mills and Fan 2006); but again these programmes (PRDP, ALREP, NUSAF, KALIP) look at the intermediate gains and improving livelihoods while also ensuring that the people are food secure and self sustaining-implying agriculture takes centre stage, investment and trade are secondary.

3.0 Data and sources

The analysis for this paper is largely descriptive and utilises data from different sources. Given that this paper is in the context of post conflict era, statistics in this paper correspond to the period 2006 to date, hence referred to as the “post-conflict period” in Northern Uganda.

3.1 Investment data

Data on investment is from the Uganda Investment Authority (UIA) on fiscal year basis. That is from 2006/07 to latest available data. This information is used to interrogate the patterns and nature of investments being undertaken in Northern Uganda with the aim of identifying investment gaps that need to be filled to ensure an industrialised Northern Uganda. It is important to point out that while it would have been ideal to provide other forms of investments by the people in the region, domestic home grown investments, statistics are not available.

3.2 Trade data

Data on various trade indicators for the Northern region is from the Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS) and Uganda Revenue Authority (URA). Specifically, the Customs Department of the URA is the principal source of trade data as over 90 percent of external trade data are obtained from this source. The data collected is mainly on visible trade. This is collected using the Single Administrative Document (SAD) through the Direct Trade Input (DTI) Centres using the Automated System for Customs Data (ASYCUDA)++ system by clearing agents on

behalf of the importers and exporters. Also Form 88 (F88) is used to capture imports of small goods. However, supplementary sources are used to ensure complete coverage. This is because not all transactions are subject to customs surveillance and control. In addition, the Informal Cross Border Survey (ICBT) has since 2004 been used as an additional source of external trade statistics that is not recorded by customs. It is worth noting that a lot of data flows have been observed and data is collected through this survey approach. Therefore, the URA Customs Department collects the formal trade data while informal trade⁴ data is collected by UBOS in collaboration with Bank of Uganda (BOU).

Formal Trade data is collected through all the gazetted border points by the Customs Authority bordering Uganda and her neighboring countries of Tanzania, Kenya, DR Congo, Rwanda and South Sudan. In the same way, informal trade data is collected from all the border points bordering Uganda and the neighbours, but informal data provides information on cross border trade, whether the border is gazetted or not. Below, Map 1 shows Uganda's Major border posts. Please note that there also exists inland gazetted trade posts but this map only shows those major ones at border points. These border posts represent the points where over 90 percent of Uganda's formal and informal exports and imports pass through. Trade trends and composition of goods analysis covers the post-conflict period, 2006 to 2014, and uses the latest publically available data.

⁴ Informal trade here means trade that is not recorded officially by customs at the border and does not necessarily mean illegal trade. Many informal trading activities are totally legal, going through customs but not officially recorded due to small quantities traders carry.

Map 1: Uganda's major border posts

Source: UBOS, 2016

4.0 Features of investment and trade through Northern Uganda

This section includes a comprehensive assessment of investment and trade performance in Uganda's Northern region. This helps us understand how the region has fared in recent years after conflict. The caveat here is that trade statistics within the region by the local people are not readily available as such. Proxy indicators such as exports and imports both formal and informal through the region have been used to provide an indication on how robust the post conflict recovery has been. It is argued in literature that if peace has returned, then sectors such as trade and investment should show robustness and free movement of people within and across borders (Brown et al. 2008; Collier 2009).

Such analysis over a certain period of time enables us to comprehend if the end of conflict has brought more trade within and across the region and its origin. This signals if there is untapped potential to increase trade and the region's strategic position in intra-regional trade and the benefits this yields for the local people. Sub sections 4.1 and 4.2 analyse the patterns and nature of investments and trade in and through the region.

4.1 Analysis of nature and form of investment

According to the World Development Report (WDR 2005), the various aspects of the investment climate can be usefully divided into four broad policy pillars as seen in Figure 2. Each can be an important contributing factor to, or binding constraint on, the viability of the investment and trade. For the pillars to be effective, an enabling environment in terms of supporting institutions, governance, political economy, capacity to implement and social capital aspects have to be addressed. Mills and Fan (2006) provide detailed insights into the pillars of investment with a post-conflict lens.

Figure 2: Pillars of investment climate

Source: World Development Report (WDR) 2005 and Mills and Fan (2006)

Trends in investments

From the above perspective, it is vital to analyse the investments taking place in the region by size because the pillars mentioned in Figure 2 are sufficient. Data from various sources of UIA on the number of licensed projects by regions shows that broadly, the Northern region received the least number of licensed projects both by domestic and foreign investors (Table 1) and the trend has been erratic. In particular, there is an increased interest by foreign investors in the North where on average about 6.3 percent of total projects licensed in 2012/13 and 2013/14 were in the region. This has been attributed to growing investor's confidence and sustained peace in the region (UIA, 2014), a key pillar in attracting investment. However, obtaining a licence does not necessarily translate into actual investments taking place, implying that peace and security alone does not translate into investments taking place. For example, domestic investments alone in the North are not growing (Table 1). This alludes to the possibility that the local people are also not obtaining licence to invest within the region as investments are both small and highly informal. Capacity to invest and erratic access to finance and infrastructure are cited as the biggest impediments next to obtaining land. Mills and Fan (2006) assert that informal sector activity tends to be less efficient, with lower levels of investment, fewer economies of scale and a more localised customer base. In short, by pushing enterprises into the informal economy, conflict acts as a heavy drag on economic activity.

Table 1: Regional distribution of domestic and foreign owned licensed projects, (%)

	2006/07	2007/08	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2011/12	2012/13	2013/14
Domestic								
Central	-	84.9	84	72.7	76.1	67.6	66.7	-
Eastern	-	7.5	6.9	14.1	10.2	14.3	18.1	-
Northern	-	3.2	0.7	4.2	2.4	5.7	2.8	-
Western	-	4.3	8.3	9.1	11.8	12.3	9.7	-
Foreign								
Central	-	92.6	87.8	86.6	82.4	84.1	80.1	83
Eastern	-	2.7	5.7	8.1	9	8.4	8.1	6
Northern	-	2.1	1.4	0.5	3.2	0	6.6	6
Western	-	2.3	5.5	5.1	5.3	7.6	5.3	2

Source: Compiled from various UIA Statistical Abstracts.

Of the licensed projects, planned investments in the region indicate a steady growth since 2008/09 despite the projects still being few (the value was US\$ 7.0 million) and reached US\$ 87.2 million in 2012/13 but then declined to US\$ 55.5 million in 2013/14 (Figure 3). These represented 0.3 percent, 7.8 percent and 2.7 percent out of the total planned investments in Uganda, respectively. According to UIA (2014),

the 2012/13 performance was attributed to a once off huge investment in manufacturing and mining and quarrying sectors where this was undertaken in Amuru District and accounted for 3.1 percent of total planned investments.

Figure 3: Planned investments for Uganda's Northern region, USD (million)

Source: UIA, Various statistical abstracts

Nature and impact of investments

Actual realised investments are very minimal. Actual investments by value have been highest in wholesale, retail and accommodation services (US\$201 million in 2012/13) due to high investments in hotel and hospitality services but these declined to US\$ 9.2 million in 2013/14 because many investments that were planned did not materialise. Manufacturing was high due to heavy investments in the mining and quarrying sector, especially in Karamoja sub region. The poor performance in actual investments in 2013/14 was attributed to a general decline in actual projects implemented due to lack of project financing, land resettlement of squatters and land compensation, delays in acquisition of various permits and business licenses, and delays in acquisition of suitable agricultural land. The partial closure of the land registry in the first half of 2013 also affected some projects (UIA, 2014).

For example, the Northern town of Lira has seen explosive growth, over just four to five years in oil seed processing plants and the sector is now providing cash incomes to an estimated 150,000 out-grower households, and continues on an upward trajectory. These, and similar

investments across the North⁵, suggest that conditions are becoming more favourable to the type of transformational growth that has been predicted (Hausmann *et al.* 2014). According to an excerpt from an interview with Mukwano industries in the GoU/DFID (2014) they describe the Northern town of Lira's 'oil seed revolution' in this way:

Mukwano's vegetable oil operations in Lira began with the establishment of a factory/oil mill ... Over US\$20m was invested in state of the art technology and ultra-modern machinery. A "win-win" partnership has been achieved by Mukwano working hand-in-hand with over 60,000 smallholder growers that have been organized into around 2,000 producer groups. Around 200 highly trained parish level extension personnel (site co-ordinators) and 12 district level extension personnel (extension co-ordinators) ensure that the smallholder growers benefit from the transfer of knowledge and skills. There has been a 400 percent increase in sunflower production in the region between 2005 and 2009. Annual expenditure on direct procurement of grains such as sunflower, soya and maize from farmers in the region stands at around UGX 60 billion (£15m). A second phase of expansion in Lira is planned which will see further investment of US\$20m over the next 3 years with a focus on oil refining, packaging, animal feeds processing and power co-generation. Source: GoU/DFID (2014)

Two other companies, Mount Meru and Nile Agro, have also invested in plants of a similar size, and up to 15 other smaller companies have also established oil milling facilities in the same town. The effect on poverty is significant: 72,000 farmer households⁶ are receiving an important cash income from Mukwano (a rough estimate is \$400/year/household based on the Gou/DFID 2014) and an estimated further 100,000 households are benefitting from one or more of the other companies, reaching as many as one million people. There are some reasons to be cautious about continued explosive growth in Lira (a market approaching capacity) or its replication potential elsewhere in the North (Lira is geographically well placed, and is perceived to have a more business-like culture), but the example and potential it demonstrates is striking. Other areas of the north have seen similar, if smaller investments, but also growth in more commercial scale farming. Ownership of these investments is often not associated with the local people within the region.

Access to finance is particularly acute in the North, both in terms of added risk of the environment, and in the lack of suitable lending opportunities. The EPRC (2013) FINSCOPE survey shows financial exclusion at 23 percent in the North compared to a national average of

⁵The Gulu Agricultural Development Company currently reaches 60,000 out growers; several similar schemes are currently under development, while sales of agricultural inputs to the North appear to be growing significantly.

⁶ A recent record keeping exercise of Mukwano's identified a total of 72,000 out growers in the last growing season.

15 percent, and the highest proportional use of informal lending. Investment in commercial farming is extremely limited, despite large areas of under-developed arable land, due to weak, complex land governance, and insecure tenure. Generally, the political economy of the post-conflict environment influences reform efforts. In particular, the nature of private sector participants in a post-conflict environment may differ from a non-conflict situation (Mills and Fan 2006). For example, because the political economy of land in the region is so fraught and complex; it is unlikely that the investment from local and foreign sources will go far unless the land acquisition process is streamlined (UNDP 2015). Box 1 illustrates the land constraint in the region as a constraint to promoting investment.

Box 1: Land in transforming the North

Plans of land use seem to be driven by political imperatives in the North. For example, when Madhivani started to use the land in Amuru, politicians interfered and up till now the investment has failed to take off. The need to be open about land use (security of land and security of people who use the land) for economic use and not political gain and encouraging acquisition of certificate of customary tenure in addition to stop instilling fear in the grassroots people that investor usage will lead to deprivation of people from their land is vital. Such a move will make the locals more positive on land use for investment and lead to big opportunities on its use that will transform Northern Uganda.

The fear is that issuance of a certificate of land ownership will encourage migration within the country as people from other parts of Uganda will come and take over their land as other regions understand the value of land. But inflow of external investments on land that is based on recognition of its tenure status in the community, and that which is based on a win-win situation is what the region needs. So this will require a lot of sensitization on land and developing a common understanding amongst the Acholi on what this land can do for them with their full participation.

Source: KIIs 2015

“However, just because cultivating is common does not mean that all households benefit equally” (UNDP 2007). For example, the security of access to land may have significant implications on the type and intensity of cultivation as well as the level and scale of corresponding investment. This is appositely illustrated by the complications and setbacks experienced by large companies like Mukwano and Madhivani when they attempted to acquire land in northern Uganda (Box 1).

Generally, investments in the region are low due to many challenges, some of which include: the nature of land ownership largely communal, making it hard for potential investors to acquire land. Low skilled human capital, political interference in land acquisition and usage, poor work culture and social cultural norms form part of the many

challenges the region faces in attracting meaningful investments. Specifically, the North has the highest numbers of persons with no formal education, 0.72 million; it has an equally high number with at least some primary education-1.7 million (UBOS 2014); this makes the population largely unskilled and less attractive to an employer. For investments to accrue in a region, availability of skilled local labour force is an added advantage. Furthermore, the land question if not addressed quickly, will impede private resources (both domestic and foreign) going into the North (UNDP 2007, 2015).

4.2. Performance of trade through Northern Uganda⁷

In this sub section, we note that both formal and informal trade are sensitive to changes in local security conditions. Even relatively small scale security incidents, if targeted to specific groups such as Ugandan traders, generated a substantial withdrawal of trading activities given the sparse fixed investments associated with informal trading. Thus, analysis in this subsection utilises data aggregated from the different border posts and points of entry and exit in the Northern Uganda districts. The data is collapsed at the 2 digit grouping for commodities (goods) irrespective of border post in the North. A discussion of formal and informal trade trends and nature substantiates this in two distinct sub sections below.

Formal trade through Northern Uganda

Economic interdependence through regional trade affects food security at the regional level. Given the short-term supply capacity constraint in Uganda, the export boom due to the demand for agricultural food products through Northern Uganda especially to South Sudan had created supply shortages in some districts in Uganda and raised domestic food prices (Carrington 2009). For instance Carrington (2009) argues that it has induced an expansion of agricultural production in Uganda but also attracted more imports of agricultural products from DRC. Figure 4 shows formal exports and imports trade through Northern Uganda from 2005-2014 in US\$ million. The major border posts through North for which formal exports are recorded are Bibia, Elegu, Goli, Moyo, Oraba, Paidha, Vurra and the destination countries are Belgium, Burundi, Canada, Central African Republic, China, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Eritrea, France, Germany, Greece, Haiti, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, Kenya, Korea, Malaysia,

⁷ Trade through the region implies that we combine trade taking place within and passing through the region. Statistics separating trade within the region alone are not available. Nonetheless, this provides a good synopsis on whether post-conflict recovery is fostering trade as spillover effects to indigenous people from these activities cannot be underestimated nor do we measure them in this paper.

Pakistan, Portugal, Russia, Rwanda, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, South Sudan, Sudan, Tanzania, United Arab Emirates (UAE), United Kingdom (UK), and USA.

Formal exports through the North have steadily increased since war ended in 2006. 2013 had the highest record of exports by value (US\$ 432.6 million) but declined in 2014 to US\$ 354.6 million. The decline is attributed to the insurgencies in South Soudan and the high level of insecurity Ugandan traders were exposed to, prompting many to return home, stalling goods trade from Uganda to Sudan. Formal imports performance from neighbouring countries (Sudan and DRC Congo) have steadily declined since 2009 (at US\$15.2 million) to US\$2.94 million in 2013 and gained in 2014 to US\$5.45 million (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Formal trade through Northern Uganda by Value (US\$ million)

Source: URA, 2016

Figure 5: Formal trade through Northern Uganda by Volume ('000)

Source: URA, 2016

Yoshino *et al.* (2011) posit that the demand growth in South Sudan together with lack of local production capacity led to a sharp increase in cross-border trade between Sudan and, in addition, sustained peace in Northern Uganda has acted as an additional factor which has contributed to the growth of cross-border trade between DRC, Sudan and Uganda. Stagnating formal imports performance is partly attributed to the direct cross-border transactions with north-eastern DRC due to LRA activities which are in close proximity to Ugandan

border posts. As Figure 5 shows, Uganda’s total formal exports through the North declined, partly driven by the decline of exports to Sudan in 2009 due to several the reasons. For example, the import controls imposed by the Central Bank of Sudan to lessen foreign exchange pressures and safeguard foreign exchange reserve position of the Republic of Sudan as a whole, which led to a decline of Sudan’s overall formal imports by 20 percent in 2009. A slight recovery in formal imports is recorded in 2010 in light of a normalized level of the oil revenue (Yoshino *et al.* 2011).

Sudanese formal exports through Northern Uganda are negligible compared to Ugandan formal exports to Sudan. While formal exports from Uganda to Sudan were US\$170.3 million in 2008, imports from Sudan through Northern Uganda were estimated to be as much as US\$0.08 million in the same year (Table 2). Furthermore, Uganda based only on its trading posts through the North (both in land and at borders) imports more from DRC than from Sudan and yet it exports more to Sudan than DRC. A similar trend is observed in volumes of formal trade through the north to her neighbours (Table 3). This implies that Uganda’s biggest market is Sudan, in particular South Sudan which share borders with Northern Uganda.

Table 2: Formal exports and imports Values through Northern Uganda by destination and origin, (\$ millions) 2005-2014

	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Exports										
Congo Brazzaville	0.19	2.25	7.66	4.05	1.88	-	-	-	-	-
D.R. Congo	4.54	12.83	32.75	33.87	34.63	52.98	42.04	62.91	84.29	49.26
South Sudan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	17.52	171.68	260.78
Sudan	11.21	30.19	86.26	170.34	137.85	155.01	260.15	334.81	176.15	43.92
Imports										
Congo Brazzaville	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
D.R. Congo	1.00	0.00	0.02	0.24	0.60	1.18	1.48	2.38	0.97	1.24
South Sudan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.01	0.27	1.40
Sudan	-	-	0.11	0.08	0.31	3.77	2.95	1.60	0.80	0.67

Source: Authors own compilation based on URA trade datasets, 2016

Table 3: Formal exports and imports volumes through Northern Uganda by destination and origin, (Net weight'000) 2005-2014

	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Exports										
Congo Brazzaville	270.1	2,535.2	7,260.5	5,427.2	2,412.5	-	-	-	-	-
D.R. Congo	8,679.7	17,188.5	45,523.5	38,607.8	47,775.0	117,782.2	55,671.4	83,537.7	139,263.5	71,906.0
South Sudan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	34,732.0	234,212.6	427,848.9
Sudan	6,513.5	50,659.1	210,767.5	315,566.5	279,394.6	257,273.4	359,638.5	490,953.9	245,484.7	66,886.9
Imports										
Congo Brazzaville	-					-	-	-	-	-
D.R. Congo	1,340.1	27.0	11.9	1,766.6	3,564.6	4,365.4	4,570.3	5,922.7	4,317.9	3,706.4
South Sudan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	19.9	297.4	620.6
Sudan	-	-	57.0	796.7	1,829.2	6,521.3	14,589.5	4,402.1	2,446.3	1,399.5

Source: Authors' own compilation based on URA trade datasets, 2016

Note: The Ugandan customs points, Oraba and Bibia and the DR. Congo Posts with Uganda are Lia, Wura and Goli

The leading formal exports through Northern Uganda that yield the highest value for the years of analysis can be broadly categorized as food and other consumer non-durables and construction materials. These include: sugar and sugar confectionery; cereals; Prod Mill Industry; Malt; Starches; Inulin; Wheat Gluten; Salt; Sulphur; Earth & Stone; Plastering Mat; Lime & Cement; Beverages, Spirits and Vinegar; Vehicles O/T Railw/Tramw Roll-Stock, Pts & Accessories; Iron and Steel; Animal/Vegetable Fats & Oils & their Cleavage Products and others (see Annex Table A.1 and A.2). The same categorisation applies to leading **formal imports**⁸ with the consistent goods traded through Northern Uganda being: Wood and Articles of Wood; Wood Charcoal Mineral fuels; Iron and steel; Other Made Up Textile Articles; Sets; Worn Clothing etc.; Nuclear Reactors, Boiliers, Mchy & Mech Appliance; Parts; Electrical Mchy Equip Parts thereof; Sound Recorder etc.

As highlighted throughout this paper, even when the binding constraints (such as land, energy, skills, finance etc) are overcome, the linking of local farmers to bigger stable markets has until now, remained a challenge. However, even with the opening of the 'Northern Corridor' with trade to South Sudan, the content and intensity of trade is generally dictated by the demands of the Juba market and not within the region. As such, the reoccurrence of conflict in the neighbouring state can and has had an effect on economic activity in Northern Uganda; the 2016 insurgency in Juba in July is the most recent example to illustrate this. Formal trade is practically at a standstill through the North to South Sudan.

⁸ Due to large data, detailed tables on formal imports by commodity, country, and border post can be availed on request from 2005-2014-volumes and value (USD)

Informal Cross Border Trade through Northern Uganda

Carrington (2009) highlights that the return to agriculture of formally displaced persons in the North has resulted in an increase in informal food trade in the region. Based on the UBOS's survey data, the major informal unrecorded exports from Uganda to DRC, Sudan and South Sudan are similar to those recorded for formal exports. The major border posts for informal trade are Elegu, Goli, Oraba, Paidha, Vurra, Odramachaku. Informal exports through Northern Uganda dropped substantially from US\$ 344.6 million in 2009 to US\$ 97.6 million in 2010 (Figure 6). Observed country level dynamics during 2010 to 2012 reveal that a substantial number of Ugandan traders withdrew from South Sudan due to the harsh business environment they were operating in (also in since July 2016). Tensions and deteriorating relations through increasing harassments and a series of violent acts against Ugandan traders by the Dinka drove informal exports down. Yoshino *et al.* (2011) also assert that there were also fears of potential insecurity from the Sudanese general election in April 2010 as well as the run-up to the referendum in early 2011. There have been signs of return of Ugandan traders to South Sudan since the peaceful conclusion of the referendum in early 2011, shown by the gain in informal exports in 2013 and 2014 (Figure 6), implying that informal trade through the region is highly sensitive to changes in local security conditions.

Figure 6: Informal cross border trade through Northern Uganda (\$ million), 2005-2014

Source: Authors own compilation based on UBOS trade datasets 2016

Note: The Ugandan customs points, Oraba; The DR. Congo Posts with Uganda are Odramachau, Paidha, Wura and Goli

Despite the general decline in Uganda's informal exports, Sudan remains Uganda's largest trading partner, dominated by South Sudan. In 2013, there was a remarkable recovery in exports largely driven by the recovery of Uganda's exports to Sudan for both formal and informal trade combined (Table 2, 3 & 4). The bilateral trade between Uganda and South Sudan is highly asymmetric with the volume of informal exports through Northern Uganda to Sudan being disproportionately larger than the volume of exports going in the reverse direction (Table 4). Consumption and construction booms in post-conflict South Sudan, and a sharp increase in demand coupled with lack of local production capacity are the driving force behind this increase (Yoshino *et al.* 2011).

Table 4: Informal trade through northern Uganda by Country of destination and origin, Value (\$ millions)

Value (in \$ million)	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
<i>Exports</i>	18.40	41.92	187.93	322.90	344.63	97.65	46.23	66.21	155.46	144.95
D.R. Congo	9.30	34.08	30.63	24.52	20.44	25.47	27.78	37.66	24.64	25.48
Sudan	9.11	7.84	157.30	298.38	324.18	72.18	18.44	28.55	130.82	119.47
<i>Imports</i>	9.38	6.81	10.58	12.53	12.98	11.57	10.23	9.03	12.93	12.48
D.R. Congo	8.56	6.31	9.43	9.39	11.91	11.34	10.04	8.72	7.37	8.63
Sudan	0.82	0.50	1.15	3.14	1.06	0.24	0.19	0.31	5.56	3.85

Source: Authors own compilation based on UBOS trade datasets, 2016

Note: The Ugandan customs points, Oraba. The DR. Congo Posts with Uganda are Odramachau, Paidha, Wura and Goli

The leading *informal* cross border trade exports through Northern Uganda are: Edible Vegetables and Certain Roots and Tubers; Edible Fruit and Nuts; Peel of Citrus Fruit or Melons; Cereals; Prod Mill Industry; Malt; Starches; Inulin; Wheat Gluten; Beverages, Spirits and Vinegar; Salt; Sulphur; Earth & Stone; Plastering Mat; Lime & Cement; Footwear, Gaiters and the Like; Parts of Such Articles; Other Made Up Textile Articles; Sets; Worn Clothing etc.⁹

We note that there is a high level of complementarity between formal trade and informal trade, which underlines the similarity in products traded formally and informally. Informal trade activities can take place as stand-alone cross border transactions such as crossing borders outside of the areas covered by border posts. But in many cases, informal trade takes place next to formal trade at border posts and, in ways, informal trade activities are linked with formal trade activities. The same goods can cross the border formally or informally, by foot, bicycle, motorbike, passenger car, bus, carried in small quantities, and can, thus, be exempted from the procedures at Customs.

Spillovers of trade activities

According to Gelsdorf *et al.* (2012), growth of trade and trade routes in the region has also seen an increase in the number of financial service providers like banks and businesses expanding into the region. These include the Kenya Commercial Bank (KCB), which has also established operations in Southern Sudan. KCB officials narrate that it was prudent to establish a branch in Gulu (loosely referred to as the capital city of Northern Uganda) to meet the increasing demand from business people for financial services through which they can safely transfer money between Northern Uganda and Juba (Carrington 2009). However, in spite of this increased economic activity, the “transformation of the economy and society at broader levels is still limited” (Ahikire *et al.* 2012). Over and above growth and return of the pre-war economic activities (farming, charcoal burning, alcohol brewing), Bozzoli *et al.* (2011) note that there is still a lack of major industrial activity that more of the local population can be a part of. For example, the growth of the mining and natural resource sector in sub regions such as Karamoja still leaves out a large part of the local population because of the skills level required to operate at the higher end of the industry, consequently leading more people to partake in small-scale artisanal mining. In fact, upon closer scrutiny it is evident in the literature that despite the introduction of larger companies into the market, the majority of trade

⁹ Due to large data, detailed tables on informal exports and imports by commodity, country, and border post can be availed on request from 2005-2014

is actually carried out by small-scale traders and remains predominantly informal (Carrington 2009).

5.0 Conclusion

This paper explored the status of investments and trade within and through Northern Uganda since its recovery from conflict. The discussion in this paper demonstrates that inequalities in investment persist within the region in comparison to the other regions in Uganda. Investments both domestic and foreign are ad hoc and seldom materialise. Nonetheless, potential investments in the region have been in agriculture and mining & quarrying sectors though most have been marred with challenges related to land acquisition. In addition, other forms of conflict (not discussed in this paper) particularly those related to tribal conflicts over boundaries and land, continue to hinder the attraction of meaningful investments in the region.

Findings also highlight that trade through Northern Uganda is enormous mainly due to its close proximity to South Sudan. Food stuffs and construction materials are the leading commodities being traded through the region. Informal trade far outstrips formal trade and this is in line with the statistics on the status of the region's share in the national averages. However, the insecurity in the neighbouring countries greatly hindered trade especially informal trade through the gazetted border posts in the region. This simply implies that commodity export booms through the region greatly depend on the security not only within Ugandan but also across borders. Despite the relatively high trade performance through the region, the majority of trade is actually carried out by small scale traders and remains predominantly informal and not necessarily from within the region.

However, in spite of this increased economic activity especially around trade and not investment, literature attests that there is still lack of major industrial activity that more of the region's population can be a part of. In addition, the transformation of the Northern Uganda economy and society at broader levels is still limited partly driven by the level of unskilled labour force in the region, a large part that had missed out on education in their formative years due to conflict. As a result, government and other actors in the region still have more to do in terms of strengthening institutions in the region and ensuring program initiatives for the region, but specifically to address the aspect of creating a good environment for business. The involvement of people in their own development through trade and investment is essential for boosting these activities in the region and developing a link between the two sectors for livelihood and industrial growth.

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